

1-TOM, 11-SON
DEVELOPING COMMUNICATION SKILLS THROUGH LISTENING
AND SPEAKING MATERIALS IN ENGLISH

Yangiboyeva Zilola Tulkin kizi

Student of Samarkand Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: The item under discussion shows how speaking and listening abilities are integrated to improve students' communication competence in Uzbek secondary schools and lyceums. The authors of the paper believe that since speaking and listening are always integrated in real life, educators should approach teaching these two abilities in a collaborative manner. Because these skills are not employed in integration, kids who are proficient in speaking and listening may still be unable to communicate in the language. Since this occurs in real life, using actual materials and scenarios could logically result in the integration of abilities.

Keywords: integration, listening, speaking, skills, language, integration, communicative, competence, outcome, interaction, information-gap, class, instructors.

Due to the perception that speaking and listening are too challenging, pupils typically refuse to engage in speaking and listening activities. Students may experience the real results when they are integrated through information-gap activities, which may encourage them to practice more and succeed in expressing their views. Some teachers dislike assigning information-gap exercises because they fear that the students may get unruly and create communication hurdles. Teachers should remove barriers and establish a secure, stress-free atmosphere in order to inspire and motivate their children to talk. An informationgap task is one in which students must listen while working on a task for which they lack the necessary knowledge. [1, p.p. 23-27].

Speaking in the target language necessitates performing multiple mental tasks simultaneously, such as selecting words, pronouncing them, and putting them together with the proper grammatical markers, as suggested by Flowerdew, J., and Miller, L. [2, p.p. 7-9]. Complex and nonspontaneous mental operations are needed to carry out these tasks when speaking, and failing to do so might result in hesitation, self-consciousness, fear, or even panic. This also applies to listening. To establish a welcoming environment in the classroom, the instructor should serve as the facilitator. Because each student only has a portion of the information required to finish a work, they must collaborate and share information by talking or listening to one another. This is another crucial aspect of information-gap activities.

1-TOM, 11-SON

In real life, listening and speaking are always in integration, so teachers should teach these two skills in an interacted way. Although the students may know how to listen and speak in the language, they may still not be able to communicate in this language mainly because these skills are not used in integration. Use of authentic materials and real life situations could naturally lead to the integration of skills since this is the case in real life. The aim of this article is to prove that listening and speaking both in practice phase in the classroom and in real communication situations entail unique features that result in real contributions to overall language learning. It is the teacher's task to comprehend and make use of how closely listening is related to the speaking skill and how listening can be integrated with speaking through information-gap tasks.

Integration of skills exposes English language learners to authentic language and challenges them to interact naturally in the language. By this way, English becomes a real means of interaction and sharing among people. In addition to this, it allows the teacher to color his/her lesson with varieties because the range of tasks is wider. Real success in English teaching and learning is when the learners can actually communicate in English inside and outside the classroom.

Students, at all grade levels, are encouraged to work collaboratively, finding best ways to communicate. Often, wrongly so, we assume that if a person can talk they have mastered the speaking mode of literacy; or, because they can hear they are good listeners.

We need to create learning opportunities for students to engage in meaningful speaking activities and to improve listening skills through purpose-driven strategies. Fortunately, there are various communicative activities that allow us to meet these challenges.

Communicative activities refers to the classroom activities that provide a genuine information gap and make it possible for language learners to communicate with target language in Communicative Language Teaching Approaches. In other words, communicative activities are activities that give students both a desire to communicate and a purpose which involve them in a varied use of language. They have real purposes: to find information, to break down barriers, to talk about oneself, and to learn about the culture. Even when a lesson is focused on developing reading or writing skills, communicative activities should be listening and speaking into the lesson. Communicative activities are fluency-based activities. While such activities may involve students to practice a particular grammatical form, they are likely to do more

1-TOM, 11-SON

than this. The key element is that the activity is based on a realistic situation. This could be anything from an encounter in a department store, to a group of friends discussing holiday plans, etc. Within this kind of context, students should be required to negotiate for meaning. This is likely to require multiple turn taking.

Wilson, R. claims that “the problem at present is that some of the activities being introduced as communicative activities are not communicative at all but structure drills in disguise”. Thus many teachers may think that the activities they design and use in class are communicative, but actually they are not. Therefore the features that make a real communicative activity should be focused on [5, p.p.78-87]. Based on related views about communicative activities, Sun & Cheng summarizes three common features as follows:

- Communicative activities are task-based. Task-based English teaching concentrates on communicative tasks that learners need to engage in outside the classroom.
- Communicative activities are learner-centered. The emphasis of teaching activity is on students’ initiation and interaction. Students are expected to participate in the activities as real people and take responsibility for their learning.
- Communicative activities emphasize the use of authentic language input and the teacher’s native or near native language competence in order to produce communication in the classroom.

Activities that are truly communicative also have three features in common; they are information gap, choice and feedback.

- An information gap exists when one person in an exchange knows something the other person does not. For instance, if two students both know today is Tuesday and one asks the other “What is today?” and he/she answers “Tuesday”, their exchange is not really communicative. Speakers’ choices in communication are very important. Speakers should have a choice of what they will say and how they will say it. If the teacher’s activity is tightly controlled so that students can only say something in one way; they have no choice and the exchange; therefore, seems not to be communicative.
- True communication is purposeful. A speaker can thus evaluate whether or not his/her purpose has been achieved based on the information he/she receives from his/her listener. If the listener does not have an opportunity to provide the speaker with such feedback, then the exchange is not really communicative.

From these features, it may be easier to distinguish between communicative activities and non-communicative activities. In a communicative activity, students must

1-TOM, 11-SON

have a desire to communicate, and there must be some communicative purposes to their communication. Their attention, of course, will be focused on the content of what they are saying rather than the form. They will use a wide variety of language, and the teacher will not intervene by telling students they have made mistakes in their English or correcting their pronunciation, etc. The teacher would not expect the materials which students were using would control their language. For non-communicative activities, there will be no desire to communicate, nor will students have a communicative purpose. Students are involved in repetition or substitution drills so that they can be motivated by the need to attain accuracy, not by a desire to achieve a communicative objective. In these activities, the emphasis will be on the form of the language, not the content. As a result, the teacher will intervene to ensure accuracy, and the materials used will often designed to concentrate on a particular item of language [4, p.p. 88-94].

In conclusion it's essential to underline that communicative listening and speaking activities have a strong effect on student's motivation in the lessons. They help students have more chance to talk to lots of classmates without a fear of making mistakes. In a communicative listening and speaking activity, instead of having students stand in front of class and talk to others, the teacher sets up the activity that they can talk to some other students but not the whole class and the teacher. That makes a better effect on helping students avoid their fear of making mistakes. Then they seem to be more confident to speak and eager to speak a lot.

References:

1. Anderson A. and Lynch T. Listening. Oxford: Oxford University, 1998. P.p. 23-27.
2. Flowerdew J. and Miller L. Second language listening: Theory and practice. Cambridge university press, 2005. P.p. 7-9.
3. Guariento W. and Moreley J. Text and task authenticity in the EFL classroom. ELT journal. Oct. 2001. 55 (4). P.p. 347- 351.
4. Ur P. Teaching Listening Comprehension, New York: Cambridge University Press., 2005. P.p. 88-94.
5. Wilson R. Supporting Speaking and Listening. London: London University Press., 2004. P.p. 78-87.

